

HARMLESS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953183

HARMLESS

Final webinar: Major HARMLESS achievements

11th March 2025, 14:00 – 15:30h CEST, online

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HOUSEKEEPING RULES

Thank you for accepting these rules that shall ensure a smooth running of the workshop!

- Please use a **headset and mute your microphone** if you are not speaking.
- Please **deactivate your camera** if you are not talking.
- Please **raise your hand** if you want to say something or use the **chat function**.
- If you have a **question**, please use the **chat**. Start with typing **“?”**. Based on the entries in the chat the moderator will pick up questions for further discussion within the group.

Objectives

- Showcase HARMLESS key outcomes
- Special focus on the HARMLESS Safe and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA) & our innovative Decision Support System (DSS)
- Pitch presentations of specific project results

Agenda

14:00 - 14:20

Overview of major HARMLESS results

by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

14:20 - 14:40

HARMLESS Safe and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA) / Decision Support System (DSS)

by Blanca Suarez (TEMASOL) and Susan Dekkers (TNO)

14:40 - 14:50

Q&A

by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

14:50 - 15:00

Major HARMLESS achievements – highlight pitch presentations

2 min per pitch

- **New Approach Methodologies (NAMs)**

- High Throughput Screening (HTS) including omics (AOPs),
by Roland Grafström (KI)

- Proteomics – HARN-specific toxicity profile, by Veronica Dumit (BfR)

- Predictive modelling (in vitro – in vivo), by Agnieszka Gajewicz-Skretna (UG)

- **Ecotoxicity**, by Anders Baun (DTU), José María Navas and Mona Connolly (INIA-CSIC)

- **Integration, analysis and visualization of data**, by Nina Jeliaskova (IDEA)

- **Early Warning System for regulatory preparedness**, by Andrea Haase (BfR)

15:00 - 15:25

Break-out rooms for pitch presentations

15:25 - 15:30

Outlook & future perspectives

by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

Overview of HARMLESS major results

Otmar Schmid & Tobias Stöger

Helmholtz Munich (HMGU)

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**HARMLESS Safe and Sustainable
Innovation Approach (SSIA) / Decision
Support System (DSS)**

Blanca Suarez (Temas Solutions (TEMASOL)) and Susan
Dekkers (TNO)

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Q&A

moderated by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

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Pitch presentations of major achievements

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High Throughput Screening (HTS), including omics (AOPs)

Roland Grafström

Karolinska Institute (KI)

Data generation in HARMLESS

Advanced Materials (AdNMs) & High-Aspect Ratio Nanomaterials (HARNs)

High-throughput systems toxicology for animal-free risk assessment

Predictive toxicogenomics space modeling:

- Differential expression, pathway analyses
- PTGS scoring/dose-response capture (LOELs)
- PTGS-based organ toxicity / cytotoxicity prediction using reference data, e.g., TG-GATEs, Connectivity map, and exposure e.g., therapeutic C_{max}
- PTGS component-based mode-of-action
- PTGS-MoA and AOPWiki annotations driven MIE/KE/AO and AOP analyses
- Integrative report, with AOP analysis, grouping and ranking based on potency and MoA effects of drugs/chemicals/materials

Traditional cell culture

Data points: 30-100
coverage of one endpoint

HT-screening

~25000/analysis
1-5 endpoints; HT-ToxScore

RNA-sequencing

10-40x10⁶/analysis
genome-wide coverage

HT-transcriptomics

2-10x10⁶/analysis
Reduced to whole genome
(2500-20000 genes)

Grafström et al. Altern Lab Anim. 43(5):325-32, 2015; Kohonen et al. Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol.;115(1):50-8. 2014

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Proteomic analysis of *in vivo* and *in vitro* samples

Verónica Dumit, Tobias Stobernack, Andrea Haase
German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)

Initial proteomic workflow

Label-Free Quantification

data analysis

1 maxquant.net; skyline.ms; thermofisher.com
2 matrixscience.com; msaid.de;

Advanced proteomic workflow

Tandem mass tag (TMT)

Adapted & advanced proteomic workflow

Experimental setup used for proteomic experiments

In vivo treatment with perovskites

1

Per sample group
n = 6

● ●
Printex-90 LaCoNi(8)

● ●
LaCoNiPd LaCoNiPt

liver

lung

BALF

Experiments performed by
NRCWE

In vitro treatment with nanofibers

nanofibers

silicon carbide

titanium dioxide

cell culture

24 h
45 µg / mL

Meta-Analysis of Integrated Proteomic and Transcriptomic Data Discerns Structure–Activity Relationship of Carbon Materials with Different Morphologies

Verónica I. Dumit, Yuk-Chien Liu, Aileen Bahl, Pekka Kohonen, Roland C. Grafström, Penny Nymark, Christine Müller-Graf, Andrea Haase, Mario Pink

First published: 20 December 2023 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.202306268> | Citations: 2

Pathogenic carbon nanotubes show a clear “fingerprint”

SPRINGER NATURE Link

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Home > Archives of Toxicology > Article

Towards characterization of cell culture conditions for reliable proteomic analysis: in vitro studies on A549, differentiated THP-1, and NR8383 cell lines

Toxicogenomics and Omics Technologies | Open access | Published: 12 September 2024
Volume 98, pages 4021–4031, (2024) | Cite this article

Rico Ledwith, Tobias Stobernack, Antje Bergert, Aileen Bahl, Mario Pink, Andrea Haase & Verónica I. Dumit

Different cell culture settings affect protein levels. Harmonization is key!

Advancing Nanomaterial Toxicology Screening Through Efficient and Cost-Effective Quantitative Proteomics

Tobias Stobernack, Nils Dommershausen, Víctor Alcolea-Rodríguez, Rico Ledwith, Miguel A. Bañares, Andrea Haase, Mario Pink, Verónica I. Dumit

First published: 30 May 2024 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202400420>

Advanced proteomic protocol for toxicological screening.

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Predictive modelling (*in vitro* – *in vivo*)

Agnieszka Gajewicz-Skretna, Andrzej Kedzioriski, Michal Zielinski,
Michalina Miszczak, Aleksandra Nowak

University of Gdansk (UG)

In silico descriptors (NAM)

The screenshot displays the AdMa software interface. On the left, a 'Descriptor list' window shows a table of descriptors:

No.	Name	Description
1	ZM1	first Zagreb index
2	ZM1V	first Zagreb index by valence vertex deg
3	ZM1Kup	first Zagreb index by Kupchik vertex deg
4	ZM1Mad	first Zagreb index by Madan vertex deg
5	ZM1Per	first Zagreb index by perturbation vertex deg
6	ZM1MulPer	first Zagreb index by multiplicative perturbation vertex deg
7	ZM2	second Zagreb index
8	ZM2V	second Zagreb index by valence vertex deg
9	ZM2Kup	second Zagreb index by Kupchik vertex deg
10	ZM2Mad	second Zagreb index by Madan vertex deg
11	ZM2Per	second Zagreb index by perturbation vertex deg
12	ZM2MulPer	second Zagreb index by multiplicative perturbation vertex deg
13	ON0	overall modified Zagreb index of order 0
14	ON0V	overall modified Zagreb index of order 0 by valence vertex deg
15	ON1	overall modified Zagreb index of order 1
16	ON1V	overall modified Zagreb index of order 1 by valence vertex deg
17	Qindex	quadratic index
18	BBI	Bertz branching index
19	DBI	Dragon branching index
20	SNar	Narumi simple topological index (log form)
21	HNar	Narumi harmonic topological index
22	GNar	Narumi geometric topological index
23	Xt	total structure connectivity index
24	Dz	Pogliani index
25	Ram	ramification index
26	BLI	Kier benzene-likeness index
27	Pol	polarity number
28	LPRES	log of product of row sums (PRS)
29	MSD	mean square distance index (Balaban)
30	SPI	superpendentic index
31	PII2	2D Petitjean shape index
32	ECC	eccentricity
33	AEEC	average eccentricity
34	DECC	eccentric
35	MDDD	mean distance degree deviation
36	UNIP	unipolarity
37	CENT	centralization
38	VAR	variation
39	ICR	radial centric information index
40	SMTI	Schultz Molecular Topological Index (M)
41	SMTIV	Schultz Molecular Topological Index by valence vertex deg
42	GMTI	Gutman Molecular Topological Index
43	GMTIV	Gutman Molecular Topological Index by valence vertex deg

The main window shows a 3D ball-and-stick model of a molecule. Below it, the 'MDs calculation' window is open, displaying a list of selected descriptors (5270 / 5270) and a tree view of descriptor categories:

- [1] Constitutional indices
- [2] Ring descriptors
- [3] Topological indices
- [4] Walk and path counts
- [5] Connectivity indices
- [6] Information indices
- [7] 2D matrix-based descriptors
- [8] 2D autocorrelations
- [9] Burden eigenvalues
- [10] P_VSA-like descriptors
- [11] ETA indices
- [12] Edge adjacency indices
- [13] Geometrical descriptors
- [14] 3D matrix-based descriptors
- [15] 3D autocorrelations
- [16] RDF descriptors
- [17] 3D-Morse descriptors
- [18] WHIM descriptors
- [19] GETAWAY descriptors
- [20] Randic molecular profiles
- [21] Functional group counts
- [22] Atom-centred fragments
- [23] Atom-type E-state indices
- [24] CATS 2D
- [25] 2D Atom Pairs
- [26] 3D Atom Pairs

A green callout box highlights the text: **>1000 molecular descriptors per AdMa**.

ELECTRONIC PROPERTIES

$$[\hat{T} + \hat{V}_{ee} + \hat{v}]\Psi(M) = E(M)\Psi(M)$$

where $M = N - 1, N, N + 1$ number of electrons, \hat{T} kinetic energy of electrons, \hat{V}_{ee} electron-electron repulsion, \hat{v} external potential (nucleus-electron attraction)

- ▶ Ground-state $\Psi(N)$ yields density $n(\mathbf{r})$
- ▶ Ionization energy $IP(N) = E(N - 1) - E(N)$
- ▶ Electron affinity $EA(N) = E(N) - E(N + 1)$
- ▶ Band gap $\Delta_{\mu}[n] = IP(N) - EA(N) = E(N + 1) + E(N - 1) - 2E(N)$

Band gap as the functional of ground state $n(\mathbf{r})$ density N -electron system (expanded in perturbative series with respect to e^2)

$$\Delta_{\mu}[n] = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} c_i[n] = \underbrace{\varepsilon_{N+1}[n] - \varepsilon_N[n]}_{c_0[n]} + \underbrace{\langle \phi_{N+1} | \hat{v}_x^{HF} - \hat{v}_x^{DFT} | \phi_{N+1} \rangle - \langle \phi_N | \hat{v}_x^{HF} - \hat{v}_x^{DFT} | \phi_N \rangle}_{c_1[n]} + \dots$$

where $\varepsilon_{N+1}[n]$ and $\varepsilon_N[n]$ are the **LUMO** and **HOMO** KS-eigenvalues derived from KS-DFT for the ground-state of N -electron system, respectively.

Ionization potential; Electron affinity; Energy band gap; Electronegativity; Chemical potential; Electrophilicity; etc.

Types of predictive models

> 100 in silico models

Objective: Predict in vivo toxicological response from comprehensive set of NAMs data

- Even a large suite of in vivo-validated NAMs may not allow us to always predict in vivo toxicity

Types of predictive models:

- [Q]SARs: qualitative and quantitative models
- Local and global models
- Multiple modeling approaches: linear and nonlinear regression; k-nearest neighbors; kernel regression; decision tree classification and regression; Naïve Bayes, etc.

Most predictive descriptors:

- Electronic properties: band gap energy, valance band; conduction band; electronegativity
- Phys/chem properties: aspect ratio; BET surface area; ROS production

From in vivo anchorage of NAMs to „Predictive modeling“

NAMs of AdMa

IN CHEMICO

IN VITRO

PHYS-CHEM
PROPERTIES

IN SILICO

In silico model

Predicted in vivo response

Doses: 1, 2, 6, 14, 18, 43, 54, 128, 162 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mouse}$
Various time points: 1d, 3d, 7d, 28d, 90d

True in vivo response

IN VIVO

Predictive in vivo model - 72 HARMLESS materials

	Goodness of fit (training data)				Predictivity (validation data)			
	R ²	RMSE _c	Q ² _{CV}	RMSE _{CV}	Q ² _{Ext}	RMSE _P	MAE	CCC
TDNA% BAL	0.84	2.15	0.69	3.01	0.91	1.51	1.28	0.95
TDNA% Liver	0.93	0.48	0.62	1.14	0.82	0.64	0.30	0.91
TDNA% Lung	0.75	1.18	0.47	1.71	0.77	1,03	0.69	0.87
Neutrophil influx	0.88	0.30	0.67	0.47	0.70	0,44	0.23	0.82

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Summary of ecotox studies

Lars M. Skjolding & Anders Baun, Denmark Technical University (DTU)

Mona Connolly & José María Navas, INIA-CSIC

Veronica Di Battista & Wendel Wohlleben, BASF

Proof-of-principle studies using Persistency, Bioaccumulation (and T) in a SSbD context

- **Persistency** evaluation = "does the material stay in the nano-range?"
 - Dissolution and agglomeration/dispersion stability
 - Dynamic system (Di Battista et al., 2023)
 - Static system (Hensel, 2023)
- The HARMLES **point-of-entry bioaccumulation** tiered testing approach:
 - Daphnia bioaccumulation studies
 - Algal-NM interaction studies
 - Confirmatory fish bioaccumulation studies
- The tiered testing approach is directly linked to the safety module in the HARMLESS SSbD approach

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Integration, analysis and visualization of data

Nina Jeliaskova

IDEA Consult

eNanoMapper.adma.ai : Towards AI-Ready data

- High degree of attention to extensive characterization of material properties and assays (SOPs, protocols)
- Data entry protocols

nature > nature protocols > protocols > article

Protocol | Published: 16 May 2024

A template wizard for the cocreation of machine-readable data-reporting to harmonize the evaluation of (nano)materials

Nina Jeliazkova, Eleonora Longhin, Naouale El Yamani, Elise Runden-Pran, Elisa Moschini, Tommaso Serchi, Ivana Vinković Vrček, Michael J. Burgum, Shareen H. Doak, Mihaela Roxana Cimpan, Ivan Rios-Mondragon, Emil Cimpan, Chiara L. Battistelli, Cecilia Bossa, Rositsa Tekevska, Damjana Drobnje, Sara Novak, Neža Repar, Ammar Ammar, Penny Nymark, Veronica Di Battista, Anita Sosnowska, Tomasz Puzyn, Nikolay Kochev, ... Maria Dusinska

[Nature Protocols](#) 19, 2642–2684 (2024) | [Cite this article](#)

Are you in search of the Template Wizard within the Nanosafety Data templates don't quite align with your experiment requirements. Enter the Template Designer, a powerful tool that enables you to create templates tailored to report experiment results. Once your 'blueprint' researchers can effortlessly generate and download Excel templates generated adhere to the FAIR data principles, including machine seamlessly converted to formats such as JSON and NeXus. The template into the eNanoMapper database, enhancing the efficiency and interoperability of your data reporting experience with the Template Designer app.

- AI based tools :
- Text mining, material annotation
- ChatAOP (in JRC140403 SKIG report)

Make the raw/processed data (pchem, in-vitro, in-vivo, in-silico) FAIR = converting to eNanoMapper data model

Self-contained and interoperable <https://www.nexusformat.org/recommended> by Research Data Alliance

Search, Index, Analyze, Predict

➤ Using the data: Customizable, Reusable and Shareable automatic workflows

- ToxFairy - automated HTS data FAIRification and analysis
- ✓ Toxicological profiles per material

nature nanotechnology Search Login

nature > nature nanotechnology > analyses > article

Analysis | Published: 20 May 2021

Towards FAIR nanosafety data

Nina Jeliazkova, Margarita D. Apostolova, ...

Penny Nymark + Show authors

Nature Nanotechnology 16, 644–654 (2021) | [Cite this article](#)

2502 Accesses | 28 Citations | 25 Altmetric | [Metrics](#)

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HARMLESS Early Warning System for Advanced Materials

Julia Prinz, Gregor Nagel, Susan Dekkers, Eugene P. van Someren, Véronique Adam, Veronica Di Battista, Blanca Suarez-Merino, Wendel Wohleben, Michael Persson, Anders Baun, Otmar Schmid,
Andrea Haase

German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)

EWS within the risk governance process for AdMa

1. Identification of **materials with concern(s)** → **Prioritization („Filter“ function)**
2. **Practical, modular and easy tool** for screening of AdMa (before or after market entry)
3. Aligned with HARMLESS SSbD facilitating the **dialogue between innovators & regulators**
4. Supported by an **online Decision Support System (DSS)**

HARMLESS Early Warning System

Case study: oxide-perovskites

Tier 0		Tier 1					
Question	Answer	Question	Simple	Elaborated	Final		
(1) Novelty of material	AdMa (not yet on the market; R&D products at Lab Phase)	8a.	Persistence	no			B
		8b.	Fibres with critical morphology	NA			
In the scope of the EWS		9.	High / enhanced reactivity	yes	yes		
		10.	Multicomponent	yes	yes		
(2) Does it consist of particles?	Yes (primary particles > 100 nm)	11.	Hazardous for human health or environment	yes	yes		A
		Route B (hazard first)		1.	Dust / aerosol release	yes	
		2.	Consumers or general population exposure	no			
		3.	Occupational exposure	yes	yes		
(3) Nano-enabled?	yes	4.	More than one form of human exposure	no			C
		ISO definition (nanostructured)		5.	Wide-dispersive use	no	
		6.	Assumed tonnage	> 1000 t	yes		
		7.	Environmental exposure	no			
(4) Category	Automotive catalyst	12g.	SDG 11.6 Air quality	yes, pos.	+1	Total: 0	D
		Comparison with conventional automotive catalysts		12h.	SDG 12.2 Natural resources		
		13.	Which legislation				
		14.	Applicability of legislation	yes			
		15.	Available / adopted methods	yes			

Summary & Outlook

1. **Practical, modular and easy tool** for screening of AdMa (before or after market entry)
 2. Identification of **materials with concern(s) → Prioritization („Filter“ function)**
 3. Aligned with HARMLESS SSbD facilitating the **dialogue between innovators & regulators**
 4. Tested using data from two HARMLESS case studies (aerogels & perovskites)
 5. Supported by an **online Decision Support System (DSS)**
- **Ongoing:** Testing/ optimisation of the HARMLESS EWS using HARMLESS case studies
 - **Outlook:** Present the concepts & outcomes to OECD. Our approach could be easily implemented in the existing Early4AdMa. – **1st workshop on 1st of April 2025**

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Breakout Groups

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Outlook & future perspectives

Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

Ongoing & Outlook Activities

- **Preparation of a Joint OECD-SUNSHINE/ SUNRISE-HARMLESS Workshop**
 - *SAVE-THE-DATE*: 1st April 2025 (online) – more information will be available soon!

- **Further work on NAM integration in HARMLESS SSIA & work on a Guidance Document**
 - **Our aim**: Present & Discuss HARMLESS SSIA (SSbD & EWS), together with relevant work of NMBP-16 sister projects DIAGONAL & SUNSHINE (which already ended) at the OECD

- **Ongoing evaluation of HTS & Omics Datasets & further work on AOP anchoring**

Ongoing & Outlook Activities

- **SETAC 2025 (11-15.05.2025, Vienna, Austria)**
 - 4 oral presentations

- **AIT conference 2025 (03-05.06.2025, Milton Keynes, UK)**
 - HARMLESS session
 - 4 oral presentations

Webinar wrap-up

LinkedIn

Twitter

www.harmless-project.eu

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- **We are open to collaboration**
- **Keep in touch with us!**

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